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POLITICS & INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS | RESEARCH ARTICLE

Evaluation of pedagogical leadership through the Vanderbilt Assessment of Leadership in Education (VAL-ED). Adaptation to the context of Higher Education in Spain

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Abstract: Pedagogical leadership has been widely recognized as an essential factor in improving educational quality. Different studies point to it as the second most influential element in student performance and outcomes after teaching practice. Although the evaluation of principal leadership is an important tool that could help to find ways to improve the effectiveness of principal leadership, the design of such evaluation tools has always been a challenge. On the other hand, when we refer to pedagogical leadership in the context of Higher Education, we find that the limited number of studies suggests that research is still insufficient. Therefore there is a need to continue to deepen this field of research, which will allow us to further explore pedagogical leadership in Higher Education, providing results that will have an impact on the effectiveness of organizational development and its improvement in all dimensions of the institution, as well as on the performance and results of the students. This study aims to translate the Vanderbilt Assessment of Leadership in Education (VAL-ED) into Spanish and adapt it to the context of Higher Education so that we can have a reliable and effective evaluation instrument that not only allows us to continue to study pedagogical leadership in this educational stage, but also to

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In order to verify the reliability of the questionnaires, the Cronbach's alpha value was calculated for each of them, obtaining the following values: 0.896 for the Supervisors questionnaire, 0.948 for the Directors/Coordinators questionnaire, and 0.938 for the teachers' questionnaire. Since all the values obtained are very close to 1, we can conclude that the three questionnaires obtained are reliable.

4. Conclusions

The main objective of this study was the translation and subsequent adaptation to the Higher Education context of the Educational Leadership Assessment tool Vanderbilt Assessment of Leadership in Education (VAL-ED). We can affirm that the questionnaire includes different items that collect the main components of educational leadership. The translation and adaptation to the context of Spanish Higher Education of the questionnaire for Vanderbilt Assessment of Leadership in Education (VAL-ED) is a valid and reliable instrument to evaluate the leadership of directors/coordinators of degrees in Higher Education.

We can affirm that the questionnaire generated is a valid questionnaire that will allow us to evaluate the pedagogical leadership of directors in the context of Higher Education, allowing us not only to assess the extent to which leadership in universities is focused on student performance and achievement, but also on possible areas of improvement that will undoubtedly improve not only the results of students, but also the results of Higher Education educational institutions.

Among the limitations of the study, it is worth noting the lack of representativeness of the sample. Given that the recruitment of participants was conditioned voluntarily at the time of participating in the study, it has not been possible to guarantee the representativeness of the entire Higher Education as a whole. It should also be noted that the sample size of respondents was not significant enough to statistically validate the questionnaires.

As already pointed out above, the small number of works that analyse the influence of educational leadership in Higher Education on the performance of students and the quality of institutions, suggests that the research is still insufficient, being manifested the need to further enhance this area of research, where it reverses the effectiveness of organizational development and its improvement in all dimensions of the institution. The translation and adaptation of the VAL-ED to the context of Higher Education is, therefore, a useful tool to analyse the leadership of managers in Higher Education, as well as when it comes to helping to focus on where to direct future areas of improvement in leadership in Higher Education. Consequently, being able to count on this tool will allow us to continue working in compliance with the necessary scientific standards that guarantee the quality of knowledge, in order to be able to know, if the effects of pedagogical leadership that have been observed in the performance and performance of students in compulsory education centers, are also evident in the context of Higher Education, as well as its influence on improving the quality of them.

This study comes from a broader research, derived from a doctoral thesis work in execution entitled: "Analysis of pedagogical e-Leadership in Distance University Education. Implications for educational improvement".

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Authors' contributions

Conceptualization: FLL, JMPF, MPCR and IAD; Data curation: JMPF and MPCR; Formal analysis: JMPF and IAD; Funding acquisition: MPCR and MPCR; Investigation: FLL, JMPF, MPCR and IAD; Methodology: MPCR and IAD; Project administration: FLL and MPCR; Resources: MPCR and IAD; Software:

JMPF and IAD; Supervision: FLL and MPCR; Visualization: JMPF, MPCR and IAD; Writing - original draft: FLL, JMPF, MPCR and IAD; Writing - review & editing: FLL, JMPF, MPCR and IAD.

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